

UCH O'LCHAMLI NILPOTENT ALGEBRANING DIFFERENSIALLASHI

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10801644>

Annotatsiya. Differenziallashtirish matematikaning fundamental tushunchalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Differenziallashtirish algebra fanida ham muhim o'rin tutadi. Differenziallashtirishning turli umumlashmalari mavjud. Bular sarasiga antidifferenziallashtirishlar, δ -differenziallashtirishlar, ternar differenziallashtirishlar va (α, β, γ) -differenziallashtirishlar kiradi. Ushbu ishda uch o'lchamli nilpotent algebralarning differenziallashtirishi lokal differenziallashtirishi isboti bilan ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Differenziallashtirish, Algebra, lokal differenziallashtirish, chiziqli akslantirish.

Аннотация. Дифференцирование — одно из фундаментальных понятий математики. Дифференциация играют важную роль в алгебре. Существуют различные обобщения дифференциаций. К ним относятся антидифференцировки, d -дифференцировки, тройные дифференцировки и (α, β, γ) -дифференцировки. В данной работе дифференцирование трехмерных нильпотентных алгебр показано путем доказательства локального дифференцирования.

Ключевые слова: Дифференцирование, алгебра, локальное дифференцирование, линейное отражение.

Abstract. Differentiation is one of the fundamental concepts of mathematics. Differentiations play an important role in algebra. There are various generalizations of differentiations. These include anti-differentiation, d -differentiation, triple differentiation and (α, β, γ) -differentiation. In this paper, differentiation of three-dimensional nilpotent algebras is shown by proving local differentiation.

Keywords: Differentiation, algebra, local differentiation, linear reflection.

Quyida biz uch o'lchamli nilpotent algebralarning differenziallashtirishini keltiramiz.

R haqiqiy sonlar maydoni ustida aniqlangan $\{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ bazisli nilpotent algebra N_1 berilgan. Bu algebrada ko'paytirish jadvali quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$e_1^2 = e_2 \quad e_2^2 = e_3$$

N_1 algebrada ixtiyoriy x vektorni

$$x = x_1 e_1 + x_2 e_2 + x_3 e_3$$

ko'rinishda yozish mumkin. $d : N_1 \rightarrow N_1$ akslantirishni qaraylik.

1-Ta'rif. Agar N algebaradan olingan ixtiyoriy x, y elementlar uchun

$$d(x \cdot y) = d(x) \cdot y + x \cdot d(y)$$

Tenglik bajarilsa d akslantirish qaralayotgan N algebrada differenziallashtirish deb ataladi.

$d(x) = Ax$ chiziqli akslantirishni qaraylik, bu yerda $A - 3 \times 3$ o'lchamli kvadrat matritsa.

Ravshanki, agar N_1 algebaradan olingan ixtiyoriy x, y elementlar uchun

$$A(xy) = (Ax)y + x(Ay) \quad (1)$$

tenglik bajarilsa $d(x) = Ax$ akslantirish qaralayotgan N_1 algebrada differenziallashtirishdan iborat bo'ladi.

1-Teorema. $d(x) = Ax$ akslantirish N_1 algebrada differenziallashtirishdan iborat bo'lishi uchun A matritsa

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2a_{1,1} & 0 \\ a_{3,1} & 0 & 4a_{1,1} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

ko'rinishda bo'lishi zarur va yetarli.

Isbot. Zarurligi. $d(x) = Ax$ akslantirish N_1 algebrada differensiallashdan iborat bo'sin. U holda

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} \\ a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} \\ a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix}$$

Matritsa ixtiyoriy x, y vektorlar uchun (1) tenglikni qanoatlantirishi kerak.

Xususan $e_1^2 = e_2$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_1)e_1 + e_1(Ae_1) = A(e_2)$$

qaraylik:

$$Ae_1 = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} \\ a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} \\ a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} \\ a_{2,1} \\ a_{3,1} \end{pmatrix} = a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{2,1}e_2 + a_{3,1}e_3$$

$$Ae_2 = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} \\ a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} \\ a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,2} \\ a_{2,2} \\ a_{3,2} \end{pmatrix} = a_{1,2}e_1 + a_{2,2}e_2 + a_{3,2}e_3$$

$$(Ae_1)e_1 = (a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{2,1}e_2 + a_{3,1}e_3)e_1 = a_{1,1}e_2$$

$$e_1(Ae_1) = e_1(a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{2,1}e_2 + a_{3,1}e_3) = a_{1,1}e_2$$

$$a_{1,1}e_2 + a_{1,1}e_2 = a_{1,2}e_1 + a_{2,2}e_2 + a_{3,2}e_3$$

bundan

$$a_{2,2} = 2a_{1,1}, \quad a_{1,2} = 0, \quad a_{3,2} = 0, \quad Ae_2 = 2a_{1,1}e_2$$

tengliklarni aniqlaymiz.

Endi $e_1e_2 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_1)e_2 + e_1(Ae_2) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$(Ae_1)e_2 = (a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{2,1}e_2 + a_{3,1}e_3)e_2 = a_{2,1}e_3$$

$$e_1(Ae_2) = e_1(2a_{1,1}e_2) = 0$$

$$a_{2,1}e_3 + 0 = 0$$

bundan

$$a_{2,1} = 0, \quad Ae_1 = a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{3,1}e_3$$

tengliklarni aniqlaymiz.

Endi $e_1e_3 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_1)e_3 + e_1(Ae_3) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$(Ae_1)e_3 = (a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{3,1}e_3)e_3 = 0$$

$$e_1(Ae_3) = e_1(a_{1,3}e_1 + a_{2,3}e_2 + a_{3,3}e_3) = a_{1,3}e_2$$

$$0 + a_{1,3}e_2 = 0$$

bundan

$$a_{1,3} = 0, \quad Ae_3 = a_{2,3}e_2 + a_{3,3}e_3$$

tengliklarni aniqlaymiz.

Endi $e_2e_1 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_2)e_1 + e_2(Ae_1) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$\begin{aligned} (Ae_2)e_1 &= 2a_{1,1}e_2e_1 = 0 \\ e_2(Ae_1) &= e_2(a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{3,1}e_3) = 0 \\ 0 &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

bo'ldi.

Endi $e_2e_2 = e_3$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_2)e_2 + e_2(Ae_2) = A(e_3)$$

qaraylik:

$$\begin{aligned} (Ae_2)e_2 &= 2a_{1,1}e_2e_2 = 2a_{1,1}e_3 \\ e_2(Ae_2) &= e_22a_{1,1}e_2 = 2a_{1,1}e_3 \\ 2a_{1,1}e_3 + 2a_{1,1}e_3 &= a_{2,3}e_2 + a_{3,3}e_3 \end{aligned}$$

bundan

$$\begin{aligned} a_{3,3} &= 4a_{1,1}, \quad a_{2,3} = 0, \\ Ae_3 &= 4a_{1,1}e_3 \end{aligned}$$

tengliklarni aniqlaymiz.

Endi $e_2e_3 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_2)e_3 + e_2(Ae_3) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$\begin{aligned} (Ae_2)e_3 &= 2a_{1,1}e_2e_3 = 0 \\ e_2(Ae_3) &= e_24a_{1,1}e_3 = 0 \\ 0 &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

bo'ldi.

Endi $e_3e_1 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_3)e_1 + e_3(Ae_1) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$\begin{aligned} (Ae_3)e_1 &= 4a_{1,1}e_3e_1 = 0 \\ e_3(Ae_1) &= e_3(a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{3,1}e_3) = 0 \\ 0 &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

bo'ldi.

Endi $e_3e_2 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_3)e_2 + e_3(Ae_2) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$\begin{aligned} (Ae_3)e_2 &= 4a_{1,1}e_3e_2 = 0 \\ e_3(Ae_2) &= e_32a_{1,1}e_2 = 0 \\ 0 &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

bo'ldi.

Endi $e_3e_3 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_3)e_3 + e_3(Ae_3) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$\begin{aligned} (Ae_3)e_3 &= 4a_{1,1}e_3e_3 = 0, \quad e_3(Ae_3) = e_34a_{1,1}e_3 = 0 \\ 0 &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

bo'ldi.

Yetarliligi. Endi A matritsa (2) ko'rinishda bo'lsa $d(x) = Ax$ chiziqli akslantirish differensiallashdan iboratligini ko'rsataylik.

$$xy = (x_1e_1 + x_2e_2 + x_3e_3)(y_1e_1 + y_2e_2 + y_3e_3) = x_1y_1e_2 + x_2y_2e_3$$

Tenglikka ko'ra

$$A(xy) = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2a_{1,1} & 0 \\ a_{3,1} & 0 & 4a_{1,1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x_1y_1 \\ x_2y_2 \end{pmatrix} = 2a_{1,1}x_1y_1 + 4a_{1,1}x_2y_2$$

boshqa tamondan

$$Ax = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2a_{1,1} & 0 \\ a_{3,1} & 0 & 4a_{1,1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{pmatrix} = a_{1,1}x_1e_1 + 2a_{1,1}x_2e_2 + (a_{3,1}x_1 + 4a_{1,1}x_3)e_3$$

$$(Ax)y = (a_{1,1}x_1e_1 + 2a_{1,1}x_2e_2 + (a_{3,1}x_1 + 4a_{1,1}x_3)e_3)(y_1e_1 + y_2e_2 + y_3e_3) = a_{1,1}x_1y_1e_2 + 2a_{1,1}x_2y_2e_3$$

$$Ay = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2a_{1,1} & 0 \\ a_{3,1} & 0 & 4a_{1,1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \end{pmatrix} = a_{1,1}y_1e_1 + 2a_{1,1}y_2e_2 + (a_{3,1}y_1 + 4a_{1,1}y_3)e_3$$

$$x(Ay) = (x_1e_1 + x_2e_2 + x_3e_3)(a_{1,1}y_1e_1 + 2a_{1,1}y_2e_2 + (a_{3,1}y_1 + 4a_{1,1}y_3)e_3) = a_{1,1}x_1y_1e_2 + 2a_{1,1}x_2y_2e_3$$

Yuqoridagi xisoblashlar (2) tenglik to'g'riligini ko'rsatadi. **Teorema isbotlandi.**

Endi esa uch o'lchamli nilpotent algebraning lokal differensiallash tushunchasini keltiramiz.

2-Ta'rif. L algebra bo'lib undagi har bir $x \in L$ element uchun $\Delta(x) = D_x(x)$ shartni qanoatlantiruvchi $D_x: L \rightarrow L$ differensiallash mavjud bo'lsa, u holda

$\Delta: L \rightarrow L$ chiziqli akslantirish lokal differensiallash deb ataladi.

N_1 algebraning differensiallashini biz yuqorida 1-teoremada ko'rib o'tganmiz

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2a_{1,1} & 0 \\ a_{3,1} & 0 & 4a_{1,1} \end{pmatrix}$$

bu yerda quyidagi belgilashni kiritamiz

$a_{1,1} = \alpha$, $a_{3,1} = \beta$ u holda A matritsa bunday ko'rinishga o'tadi.

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2\alpha & 0 \\ \beta & 0 & 4\alpha \end{pmatrix}$$

Quyidagi teoremada N_1 algebra uchun $\Delta: N_1 \rightarrow N_1$ akslantirishni qaraylik.

2-Teorema. N_1 algebraning har qanday chiziqli lokal differensiallashi differensiallashdan iborat.

Isbot. Δ ixtiyoriy lokal differensiallashi bo'lsin. Barcha $x \in N_1$ uchun ta'rif bo'yicha $\Delta(x) = D_x(x)$ differensiallashi mavjud.

2- teoreмага ko'ra, D_x differensiallashi quyidagi matritsa ko'rinishiga ega:

$$A_x = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_x & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2\alpha_x & 0 \\ \beta_x & 0 & 4\alpha_x \end{pmatrix}.$$

Xususan $\Delta(e_1) = D_{e_1}e_1, \Delta(e_2) = D_{e_2}e_2, \Delta(e_3) = D_{e_3}e_3$

tengliklarni qanoatlantiruvchi $D_{e_1}, D_{e_2}, D_{e_3}$ matritsalar mavjud. A matritsani quyidagicha quraylik:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{e_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2\alpha_{e_2} & 0 \\ \beta_{e_1} & 0 & 4\alpha_{e_3} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Δ chiziqli bo`lgani uchun

$$\Delta(x + y) = \Delta(x) + \Delta(y), \quad \forall x, y \in N_1 \quad (3)$$

tenglik o`rinli.

Bu tenglikka ko`ra

$$\Delta(e_1 + e_2) = \alpha_{e_1+e_2}e_1 + \beta_{e_1+e_2}e_3 + 2\alpha_{e_1+e_2}e_2$$

$$\Delta(e_1) + \Delta(e_2) = \alpha_{e_1}e_1 + \beta_{e_1}e_3 + 2\alpha_{e_2}e_2$$

tengliklarga ega bo`lamiz. Bunda bazis elementlarining koeffitsientlarini taqqoslab, biz quyidagilarga erishamiz:

$$\alpha_{e_1+e_2} = \alpha_{e_1}, \quad \beta_{e_1+e_2} = \beta_{e_1}, \quad \alpha_{e_1+e_2} = \alpha_{e_2}.$$

Bundan esa $\alpha_{e_1} = \alpha_{e_2}$ bo`ladi.

(3) tenglikdan foydalanib,

$$\Delta(e_2 + e_3) = 2\alpha_{e_2+e_3}e_2 + 4\alpha_{e_2+e_3}e_3,$$

$$\Delta(e_2) + \Delta(e_3) = 2\alpha_{e_2}e_2 + 4\alpha_{e_3}e_3.$$

Yana bazis elementlarining koeffitsientlarini taqqoslab, biz quyidagilarga erishamiz:

$$\alpha_{e_2+e_3} = \alpha_{e_2}, \quad \alpha_{e_2+e_3} = \alpha_{e_3}.$$

Bundan esa $\alpha_{e_2} = \alpha_{e_3}$ bo`ladi.

Shunday qilib, biz Δ lokal differensiallash quyidagi shaklga ega ekanligini bilib olamiz:

$$\Delta = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{e_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2\alpha_{e_1} & 0 \\ \beta_{e_1} & 0 & 4\alpha_{e_1} \end{pmatrix}$$

Teorema isbotlandi. Bulardan foydalanib 3 o`lchamli nilpotent algebralarining ikki lokal differensiallanishini xam isbot qilishimiz mumkun.

REFERENCES

1. Ayupov Sh.A., Elduque A., Kudaybergenov K.K. Local derivations and automorphisms of Cayley algebras T.: Journal of Pure and Applied Algebra. - 2023. - 227(5), 107277.
2. Arzikulov F., Karimjanov. I.A. A criterion of local derivations on the seven-dimensional simple Malcev algebra. Operators and Matrices. 2022, 16(2), 495-511
3. Kadison R.V. Local derivations, Journal of Algebra T.: Vol.130, p.494-509, 1990.
4. De Graaf W.A. Classification of nilpotent associative algebras of small dimension T.: Int. J. AlgebraComput. 28(1), 2018, 133-161